

Supporting Information

Unravelling the influence of shell thickness in organic functionalized Cu₂O nanoparticles on C₂⁺ products distribution in electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction

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Table S1. Chemical composition of the samples under study, obtained from ICP-OES and elemental analysis.

Angle (2 θ)	CuODA1 (Å)	CuODA2 (Å)	CuODA3 (Å)	CuODa4 (Å)
29.7400	3.0041	3.0001	3.0072	3.0109
36.6279	2.4535	2.4586	2.4594	2.4614
42.4921	2.1275	2.1211	2.1253	2.1286
61.6506	1.5045	1.5039	1.5059	1.5054
73.7942	1.2841	1.2834	1.2840	1.2855

Table S2. Chemical composition of the samples under study, obtained from ICP-OES and elemental analysis.

	Cu (wt.%)	O (wt.%)	C (wt.%)	N (wt.%)	H (wt.%)
CuODA1	56.97	20.21	18.52	1.23	3.07
CuODA2	48.86	19.37	25.85	1.51	4.41
CuRNODA	45.28	13.51	33.87	1.73	5.61
CuRNODA4	32.28	8.46	48.26	2.73	8.32
CuODA2-Wash	83.74	13.53	2.18	0.25	0.3
CuODa2 used	54.66	22.80	21.05	1.15	1.34

Table S3. Comparison of the eCO₂RR performance of reported cathodic electrocatalysts with the activity of CuODA2

Entry	Catalyst	Electrolyte	Potential/Current	C1 FE (%)	C ₂ ⁺ FE(%)	H ₂ FE(%)	Ref.
1	Cu dendrite	CO ₂ -saturated 0.1 M CsHCO ₃	From -1.1 V to -1.5 V vs. RHE (-30 mA)	11	73	10	[1]
2	Cucurbit[6]urils-modified Cu ₂ O	0.5 M KHCO ₃	-0.7 V vs. RHE	94	0	6	[2]
3	Polyamide-incorporated Cu	1 M KOH	-0.97 V (433 mA/cm ²)	~7	90	~3	[3]
4	Histidine-functionalized Cu	1 M KHCO ₃	-2 V vs. RHE	< 5	77	21	[4]
5	Tetrahydrobipyridine-functionalized Cu	1 M KHCO ₃	-0.83 V vs. RHE	-	72	-	[5]

6	CuODA2	0.1 M KHCO ₃	-0.9 V vs. RHE	15.7	73.3	11	This work
7	N-substituted pyridinium Cu	0.1 M KHCO ₃	-1.1 V vs. RHE	-	70- 80 %	-	[6]
8	Phenanthroline- derived Cu	0.1 M KHCO ₃	-4.4 V full-cell potential	-	66	-	[7]
9	FeTPP[Cl] immobilized Cu	1 M KHCO ₃	-0.82 V vs. RHE	-	41	-	[8]
10	Dendritic polymer amine terminated- Cu	1 M KOH	-0.97 V vs. RHE	26	69	< 5	[9]
11	Bipyridine film on Cu	1 M KHCO ₃	-0.96 V vs. RHE	3	46	25	[10]
12	Thiazole functionalized Ag-Cu	0.5 M KHCO ₃	-4.5 V cell Voltage (250 mA/cm ²)	10	80	5.3	[11]
13	Tannic acid modified Cu	1 M KOH	-1.2 V vs. RHE	30	63.6	10	[12]

Figure S1. PXRD patterns of CuODA1, CuODA2, CuODA3 and CuODA4. The standard pattern of Cu₂O (PDF #05-0667) is also included.

Figure S2. TEM images of CuODA1 (a), CuODA2 (b), CuODA3 (c) and CuODA4. Insets show histogram of particle size distribution and the average particle size.

Figure S3. ATR-FTIR spectra of ODA, CuRN1, CuRN2, CuRN3 and CuRN4.

Figure S4. Cu LMM Auger spectra of CuODA1 (a), CuODA2 (b), CuODA3 (c) and CuODA4 (d).

Figure S5. Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV) of CuODA1 (a), CuODA2 (b), CuODA3 (c) and CuODA4 (d) in N₂-saturated (dashed) and CO₂-saturated (solid) 1 M KHCO₃ electrolyte.

Figure S6. PXRD patterns of CuODA2 and CuODA2-wash.

Figure S7. TEM images of CuODA2-wash samples acquired at different magnifications.

Figure S8. H_2O hydrophobicity test of CuODA2 and CuODA2-wash. It can be seen that CuODA2-wash precipitates at the bottom, while CuODA2 floats on water after 2 h.

Figure S9. Cyclic voltammograms of the samples at different scan rates from 10 to 80 mV/s.

Figure S10. Capacitive current as scan rate function of the different samples. The C_{DL} obtained is indicated for each sample.

Figure S11. CO_2 adsorption isotherms at 25 °C of CuODA2 (black) and CuODA2-wash (red).

Figure S12. In situ electrochemical Raman spectra of CuODA2 (a and b), CuODA4 (c and d) and CuODA2-wash (e and f) obtained at open circuit potential (black) and at cathode potential of -0.9 V (red). Laser excitation 785 nm.

Figure S13. Nyquist plots of CuODA1 (a), CuODA2 (b), CuODA2-wash (c), CuODA3 (d) and CuODA4 (e) collected at 20 different potentials between -0.2 to -0.8 V vs. RHE in 0.03 V increments. The spectra were collected from 0.5 Hz to 30 kHz at 10 points per decade. CO₂-saturated 1M KHCO₃ electrolyte. Pt wide and KCl-saturated Ag/AgCl were used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively.

Figure S14. a) Nyquist plot of CuODA2 measured at -0.7 V vs. RHE in the range from 0.5 Hz to 30 kHz. b) Equivalent circuit used to fit the obtained experimental data.

Figure S15. (a) Stepwise potential profile applied to the working electrode in pulsed voltammetry experiments. (b-f) Pulse responses for CuODA1 (b), CuODA2 (c), CuODA3 (d), CuODA4 (e) and CuODA2-wash (f).

Figure 16. FE for CH₂=CH₂ (black), CH₃CH₂OH (red), CH₃COOH (blue) and CH₃CH₂CH₂OH (pink) obtained from CuODA2 (solid bars) and CuODA2-wash (branded bars; w) at different current densities and using a flow electrochemical cell.

Figure 17. XRD patterns of CuODA2 before (black) and after (blue) continuous flow operation at 300 mA/cm² for 2 h.

Figure S18. HRTEM images of CuODA2 after reaction.

Figure S19. FTIR spectrum of fresh (red) and after reaction (black) CuODA2 catalyst.

References

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